

Eastern Christianity From Nicaea to Chalcedon

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Entry tags: Arianism, Early Christianity, Early Christianity, Religious Group, Nestorianism, Greek Orthodox, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Christian Traditions, Orthodox Christianity

The main task of the Council of Nicaea (325) was, on the one hand, the unanimous condemnation of the Arian heresy by all members of the Council. On the one other, the unanimous acceptance of a common and binding theological basis for the restoration of the unity of the bishops of the East. The first was achieved after long synodical procedures and discussions between the various theological groups. The second was founded on the baptismal symbol of the Church of Caesarea in Palestine, which was significantly improved after theological objections, with the addition of clearly anti-Arian terms, and was accepted after the various interventions of the emperor Constantine. The Council of Nicaea was motivated by the Trinitarian debates caused by the views of Arius (256-336). The purpose of the council was to clarify the orthodox doctrine of the Trinity as completely as possible and to faithfully express the teaching of Scripture. Arius wished to make the relation of the Father to the Son comprehensible. He and his followers equated the limits of their understanding with the limits of reality: what they could not conceive, could not therefore be. They held that the Father and the Son were of similar substances, but Jesus did not share in the same divine substance of the Father, He was not fully divine in the same way as the Father. Furthermore, Arius denied both the personality and deity of the Spirit. He considered it to be an impersonal causal agent, definitely not divine, operating as the power by which God the Father worked in creation. Although Arius's views were condemned by the Synod of Alexandria in 321, the spread of Arianism made it clear that the Apostles' Creed was no longer sufficient to protect orthodoxy. The Council of Nicaea, however, did not put an end to the controversies, but only gave the parties a new rallying point, initiating a half century of theological turmoil that was marked by political interference and changing fortunes for Athanasius of Alexandria and his supporters (the Orthodox party) and Arianism. In 381, one hundred and fifty bishops met in Constantinople, at the Council summoned by the emperor Theodosius I, with the view to declare the faith of the Nicene Creed in its original form, as the sole legitimate religion in the empire, and to condemn all forms of Arianism. The controversy between the parties at Nicaea and Constantinople raged over the proper term to express the kind of substance that the Trinity shares. The debate focused on the terms *homoiousios* and *homoousios*. Though the words look very similar, both meaning "of the same substance" they were poles apart in what they conveyed about the nature of Jesus. The difference was whether the Son is of the same or a similar substance with the Father. The Orthodox party favored the term "*homoousios*", "of the same essence," to describe the relation of the Son to the Father. This term identified the Son sharing the same essence with the Father as uncreated and essential in His existence. The Arian party preferred the term "*homoiousios*", "like the Father" or "of a like essence with the Father." Christology hence was the main concern. At the request of the Archbishop of Constantinople Nestorius, Emperor Theodosius II called together all the major bishops of the Eastern and a few of the Western Roman Empire to meet at Pentecost of 431 in Ephesus, in an effort to resolve the Christological question. Nestorius, who had been trained in the theological tradition of the school of Antioch, was reluctant in calling the Virgin Mary "Theotokos" (Mother of God) and preferred to speak of her as "Christotokos" (mother of Jesus as the one united with the Logos). Nestorius's opponents accused him for detaching Christ's divinity and humanity into two persons existing in one body, thereby denying the reality of the Incarnation. Accusations against Nestorius had focused on the claim that he divided Christ and was affirming two Christs and two Sons, a man and God, by considering the union of man and God in Christ as merely an external union. One of the main opponents of Nestorius, besides Cyril, Patriarch of Alexandria (376-444 CE), was the influential monk Eutyches of Constantinople, whose opposition to the teachings of Nestorius led him to an equally

extreme, although opposite view. He promoted an extreme Monophysite (i.e. one divine nature) teaching which denied that Christ is co-substantial with humankind. Eventually, Emperor Marcian and his wife Pulcheria summoned a Council which met at Chalcedon in 451. The Council of Chalcedon was directed at the Nestorian and Eutychian heresies, which, although concurred with the Nicene Creed, they however worked out the deity of Jesus Christ in false relation to His humanity. The error of Nestorius and his teaching was the failure to unite the two natures in one person. Each nature represented separate persons in some way possessed by the man Jesus. Eutyches and his teaching drew the opposite conclusion: the human nature was subsumed by the divine nature, producing thus a hybrid and unique kind of nature. The Council of Chalcedon affirmed the unity of Jesus's person and the duality of His natures, as well as His identity with the divine substance and pointed to four principles for an accurate understanding of Jesus: deity, humanity, the unity of one person, and the distinction of the two natures. These define the boundaries of orthodoxy.

Date Range: 325 CE - 451 CE

Region: The Eastern Byzantine Empire

Region tags: Asia Minor, Eastern Mediterranean, Levant, Greece, Mediterranean Coast, Eastern Europe, Anatolia, Byzantium

The Eastern Byzantine Empire c. 400 CE.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Richard Hanson Patrick. *The Search for the Christian Doctrine of God: The Arian Controversy, 318-381*. Chippenham-Wiltshire: Baker Academic.
- Source 2: Henry Chadwick. *The Early Church*. Pelican Books, London 1993
- Source 3: *The Acts of the Council of Chalcedon*, Translated with introduction and notes by Richard Price and Michael Gaddis, Liverpool University Press 2005.

Notes: -Frances M. Young, *From Nicaea to Chalcedon: A Guide to the Literature and Its Background*, Baker Academic; 2nd edition (April 5, 2012)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.challies.com/articles/7-councils-the-first-council-of-constantinople/>
- Source 1 Description: The First Council of Constantinople
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.arcaneknowledge.org/catholic/councils/comment02.htm>
- Source 2 Description: Commentary on the First Council of Constantinople
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.ligonier.org/learn/articles/truly-god-truly-man-council-chalcedon>
- Source 3 Description: Truly God, Truly Man: The Council of Chalcedon
- Source 1 URL: https://www.cs.mcgill.ca/~rwest/wikispeedia/wpcd/wp/f/First_Council_of_Nicaea.htm
- Source 1 Description: First Council of Nicaea

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Jesus/The-dogma-of-Christ-in-the-ancient-councils#ref1228735>

– Source 2 Description: The dogma of Christ in the ancient councils of Jesus

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.catholic.com/encyclopedia/councils-of-nicaea>

– Source 3 Description: Councils of Nicaea Respectively, the first and seventh Ecumenical Councils

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL:

<https://archive.org/details/ActaConciliarumOecumenicorum.ConciliumUniversaleChalcedonensiscomplete>

– Source 1 Description: Acta Conciliarum Oecumenicorum. Concilium Universale Chalcedonensis

– Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/aco-i-1-6-ephesenum-collectio-vaticana-165-172/ACO-I-1-6-Ephesenum-%28Collectio-Vaticana-165-172%29/page/n3/mode/2up>

– Source 2 Description: ACO I 1 6 Ephesenum

– Source 3 URL: <https://sourcebooks.fordham.edu/basis/ephesus.asp>

– Source 3 Description: Medieval Sourcebook: Council of Ephesus, 431

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.papalencyclicals.net/councils/ecum03.htm>

– Source 1 Description: Council of Ephesus (A.D. 431)

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/fathers/3810.htm>

– Source 2 Description: Council of Ephesus (A.D. 431)

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.papalencyclicals.net/councils/ecum01.htm>

– Source 3 Description: First Council of Nicaea – 325 AD

– Source 1 URL: <https://sites.google.com/site/canonsoc/home/canons-of-the-ecumenical-councils/i-nicaeanum-325>

– Source 1 Description: The Canons of the Eastern Orthodox Church

– Source 2 URL: <http://www.clerus.org/bibliaclerusonline/en/bw3.htm>

– Source 2 Description: 7 ecumenical councils

– Source 3 URL:

https://www.research.manchester.ac.uk/portal/files/51216508/The_Canons_of_the_First_Ecumenical_Counc.pdf

– Source 3 Description: The Canons of the First Ecumenical Council of Nicaea in the Manuscript IOM, RAS Syr. 34

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

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↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– I don't know

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: During the period under investigation, Christians began to divide texts into those that aligned well with the "canon" of accepted theological thought and those that were suspicious of promoting heresy. This was pivotal in finalizing the structure of the collection of works called the Bible. By the early third century, Christian theologians used or were familiar with the same 27 books found in modern New Testament editions, though there were still disputes over the canonicity of some of the writings. Thus, while there was a debate in the Early Church over the New Testament canon, the major writings were accepted by almost all Christians by the middle of the 3rd century. In 331, Emperor Constantine commissioned Eusebius of Caesarea to deliver fifty Bibles for the Church of Constantinople. Athanasius refers to scribes in Alexandria, in 340 most probably, preparing Bibles for Emperor Constans. It has been suggested that these imperial requests may have provided motivation for canon lists, and that Codex Vaticanus and Codex Sinaiticus are examples of these Bibles.

Reference: Brakke, David. "Canon Formation and Social Conflict in Fourth-century Egypt: Athanasius of Alexandria's Thirty-ninth "festal Letter"". *The Harvard Theological Review* 87, no. 4 (1994): 395–419.

Reference: Auwers, Jean-Marie, ed.. *The Biblical Canons*. Edited by Jean-Marie Auwers. Leuven: Leuven University Press, 2003.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Reference: Lane Fox, Robin. *Pagans and Christians*. Suffolk: Penguin Books, 1988.

Reference: MacMullen, Ramsay. *Christianizing the Roman Empire: A.D. 100-400*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 1977.

Reference: Freeman, Charles. *AD 381: Heretics, Pagans, and the Christian State*. London: Pimlico, 2009.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Between the years 325-451 the total population of the Byzantine Empire was about 16 to 18 millions. A large number of these people were Christians, either Orthodox or adherents of any given Christian sect/heresy. There were also many pagans, despite the various legislations against paganism.

Reference: Treadgold, Warren. *A History of the Byzantine State and Society*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press, 1997.

Reference: Mcevedy, Colin. *Atlas of World Population History*. Edited by Richard Jones. London: Penguin Books Ltd. and Allen Lane, 1978.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: A sort of religious affiliation was assigned through baptism. During the period under discussion, baptism attained precision in the 3rd and 4th centuries. While instruction on matters of faith was at first

given after baptism, believers were given increasingly specific instructions before being baptized, especially in the face of heresies in the fourth century. By the fourth and fifth centuries, a series of rites spread over several weeks led up to the actual baptism at Easter: catechumens attended several meetings of intensive catechetical instruction, often by the bishop himself, and often accompanied by special prayers, exorcisms, and other rites. Catechumens recited the Creed of on Holy Saturday to show that they had completed their catechetical instruction. At dawn, after the Paschal Vigil, they were taken to the baptistry where the bishop consecrated the water with a long prayer recounting the types of baptisms. The catechumens disrobed, were anointed with oil, renounced the devil and his works, confessed their faith in the Holy Trinity, and were immersed in the font. They were then anointed with chrism, received the laying on of hands, clothed in white, and led to join the congregation in the Easter celebration. Gradually, child baptism, using an adaptation of the rite intended for adults, became more common than baptisms of adult converts.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Christianity in the Roman Empire was illegal. Roman Emperors persecuted the Christians and their practices. However, when Constantine the Great came to power, Christianity gained prominence in Roman politics. Constantine favored Christianity and legalized its practice in the empire in 313 with the edict of Milan. Christians could henceforth be appointed to government positions. In the meantime, Emperor Julian (361-363) tried to revive the pagan religions. Julian started a religious reformation of the empire, which was intended to restore the lost strength of the Roman state. He supported the restoration of Hellenistic polytheism as the state religion. His laws tended to target wealthy and educated Christians. Emperor Valens (328-378) had to confront the theological diversity that was beginning to create division in the Empire. He was baptized by the Arian bishop of Constantinople before he set out on his first war against the Goths. While the Nicene Christian writers of his time identified Valens with the Arian party and accused him of persecuting Nicene Christians, modern scholarship describes Valens as primarily interested in maintaining social order. His successor Theodosius I made Nicene Christianity the state religion of Rome and suppressed the Arians. In 380, Trinitarian Christianity was made the official religion of the Roman Empire by Theodosius I (347-395) with the edict of Thessalonica. This later determined that only Christians who believed in the consubstantiality of God the Father, Son and Holy Spirit could consider themselves as "catholic" and have their own places of worship officially recognized as "churches". On the contrary, all deviants were labeled heretics and described as out of their minds and insane. Theodosius II (401-450), who wished to resolve doctrinal controversies regarding the nature of Christ, appointed Nestorius as archbishop of Constantinople in 428. This latter quickly became involved in theological disputes. He was accused of separating Christ's divine and human natures, resulting in "two Christs", a heresy later called Nestorianism. Though initially supported by Theodosius II, he eventually lost his support.

Reference: King, Noel Quinton. *The Emperor Theodosius and the Establishment of Christianity*. Philadelphia: Westminster Press, 1960.

Reference: Wilken, Robert Louis. *The Christians as the Romans Saw Them*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 2003.

Reference: Jones, Arnold Hugh Martin. *Constantine and the Conversion of Europe*. Toronto, Buffalo, London: University of Toronto Press, 1978.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: During the first century the concept of bishop was intertwined with the concept of local priesthood. Both the role of the bishop and the authority of the role from each bishop cannot be characterized today as different even from the role of an elder of the local priesthood. During the second century, however, the concept of bishop both in terms of the bearer of theological authority and the content of the Church service seems to undergo a substantial transformation. Thus, during the second but especially during the third century, the bishop becomes the head of the local church. The primary role of the bishop was to safeguard and promote the legacy of the apostolic tradition. The second duty of the bishop was to celebrate the Eucharist, since in the sacrament of the Eucharist the experience of the real presence of Christ was manifested. The performance of the eucharistic service, at least until the third and the fourth centuries, was identified with the bishop. The bishops, as the spokesmen and heads of each local church, were responsible for the anti-heretical struggle. In this light, synodality, which began to function in the second century as a model of the apostolic council of 49, had the objective to preserve the Orthodox doctrine and to decide on organizational issues, as a result of the rapid development of Christianity, since all the bishops were also considered as the bearers of the authenticity of the apostolic tradition experienced by each local church. The historical roots of the synodal system are found in the structure and life of the first Christian communities and are connected to the Eucharistic gatherings. The fact that the development of this institution also received external influences does not in any way diminish its "biblical basis" and "apostolic origin". There was an initial connection between synodality and the Eucharist, which is also expressed by the fact that the synodical structure of the Church, from the beginning was Episcopal-centered, given that the bishop was the prefect of the local community. Due to his position in the eucharistic gathering, the bishop was the center and the representative of the local Church and at the same time the one through whom the local Church was connected with the other Churches in a wider ecclesiastical society. It was, therefore, natural for the bishop to express this unity at a synodical level as well, not as an individual, but as the head and spokesman of his Church. Thus a Council (synod) of bishops summed up the ecclesiastical experience of the whole body of the local communities, whose bishops constituted the Council.

Reference: Drake, Harold Allen. *Constantine and the Bishops: The Politics of Intolerance*. Baltimore: Johns

- ↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:
 - Yes
 - ↳ A single leader of a local community:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:
 - No
 - ↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):
 - Yes
 - ↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
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- ↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
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- ↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
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 - ↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
 - No
 - ↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
 - No
 - ↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
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↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– Yes

Notes: Recognizing the important role of the bishops, the emperors often intruded into the electoral process by imposing their candidates.

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Notes: The nominations and elections of bishops were done solely by a popular vote of all the faithful, i.e. the congregation. This system unworthy persons from becoming bishops. By the middle of the third century, however, evidence shows that women were beginning to be excluded from voting.

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– No

Notes: It should be noted however that in the case of St. Ambrose who was elected bishop of Milan in 373, it was the inspiration of the Holy Spirit that prompted his election.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Membership/Group Interactions

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↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– No

Notes: It should be noted however that in the case of St. Ambrose who was elected bishop of Milan in 373, it was the inspiration of the Holy Spirit that prompted his election.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– I don't know

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: During the period under investigation, Christians began to divide texts into those that aligned well with the "canon" of accepted theological thought and those that were suspicious of promoting heresy. This was pivotal in finalizing the structure of the collection of works called the Bible. By the early third century, Christian theologians used or were familiar with the same 27 books found in modern New Testament editions, though there were still disputes over the canonicity of some of the writings. Thus, while there was a debate in the Early Church over the New Testament canon, the major writings were accepted by almost all Christians by the middle of the 3rd century. In 331, Emperor Constantine commissioned Eusebius of Caesarea to deliver fifty Bibles for the Church of Constantinople. Athanasius refers to scribes in Alexandria, in 340 most probably, preparing Bibles for Emperor Constans. It has been suggested that these imperial requests may have provided motivation for canon lists, and that Codex Vaticanus and Codex Sinaiticus are examples of these Bibles.

Reference: Brakke, David. "Canon Formation and Social Conflict in Fourth-century Egypt: Athanasius of Alexandria's Thirty-ninth "festal Letter"". *The Harvard Theological Review* 87, no. 4

(1994): 395-419.

Reference: Auwers, Jean-Marie, ed.. The Biblical Canons. Edited by Jean-Marie Auwers. Leuven: Leuven University Press, 2003.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
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- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
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 - Field doesn't know
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- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: Although not an eschatology per se, it should be noted that the Orthodox party considered the Christological problem as key to the salvific work of Jesus. Christology in fact was central to the debate, already from the Council of Nicaea to the Council of Chalcedon. The chief concern of the Orthodox group was the relationship of Jesus's deity to the doctrine of salvation. The Nicene Fathers considered the work of salvation the type of work only God could do. Only God could save. The grace of Jesus Christ is the very grace of God Himself. As Athanasius of Alexandria pointed, no creature can be saved by a creature. How could it be the grace of God to pour out His wrath on an innocent third party? Jesus is a mediator in the full sense of revealing God himself because He is God.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The fourth century is broadly characterized as the golden age of the Patristic and consequently of Christian literature. Significant bishops and Fathers of the Church, deeply educated in both secular and christian "paideia" systematize the ethics of the New Testament and the theology of the Apostle Paul to formulate Christianity's moral attitude in the new era, after the persecutions and the sufferings. Theologians such as the three Cappadocians, Basil the Great, Gregory of Nazianzus and Gregory of Nyssa, the great rhetor John Chrysostom, Libanius's student, forged through their sermons and speeches Christian ethics. At the same time, the gradual development of monasticism helped the development of Christian morality: ascetics and ascetic communities that previously resided deep in the Egyptian desert, gradually either moved to the large urban centers, or made their presence felt through the dissemination of their ascetic teachings and their contact with the "world", as a result of the emergence of Christianity as the official religion of the Byzantine state.

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- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - No
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes

- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - No

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

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– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: Although not an eschatology per se, it should be noted that the Orthodox party considered the Christological problem as key to the salvific work of Jesus. Christology in fact was central to the debate, already from the Council of Nicaea to the Council of Chalcedon. The chief concern of the Orthodox group was the relationship of Jesus's deity to the doctrine of salvation. The Nicene Fathers considered the work of salvation the type of work only God could do. Only God could save. The grace of Jesus Christ is the very grace of God Himself. As Athanasius of Alexandria pointed, no creature can be saved by a creature. How could it be the grace of God to pour out His wrath on an innocent third party? Jesus is a mediator in the full sense of revealing God himself because He is God.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The fourth century is broadly characterized as the golden age of the Patristic and consequently of Christian literature. Significant bishops and Fathers of the Church, deeply educated in both secular and christian "paideia" systematize the ethics of the New Testament and the theology of the Apostle Paul to formulate Christianity's moral attitude in the new era, after the persecutions and the sufferings. Theologians such as the three Cappadocians, Basil the Great, Gregory of Nazianzus and Gregory of Nyssa, the great rhetor John Chrysostom, Libanius's student, forged through their sermons and speeches Christian ethics. At the same time, the gradual development of monasticism helped the development of Christian morality: ascetics and ascetic communities that previously resided deep in the Egyptian desert, gradually either moved to the large urban centers, or made their presence felt through the dissemination of their ascetic teachings and their contact with the "world", as a result of the emergence of Christianity as the official religion of the Byzantine state.

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– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):
– No

↳ Courage (generic):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
– Yes

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– Yes

- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
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- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
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- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
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- ↳ Optimism / hope:
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- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Celibacy was required only for the monks, not for the laymen and also for the clergy and more particularly for the Bishops. In fact, during the period under investigation, religious and spiritual life blossomed giving rise to monasticism, which became a way for many to strive for the evangelical ideals of asceticism. Monasticism began to influence all aspects of Church life to the point that even the laity began to adopt some of monastic customs and rules. It furthermore became common practice for spouses to separate by mutual consent when they reached old age and both went to live in monasteries. Marriage was still permitted for bishops, but the rule of celibacy for bishops was brought up at the Council of Nicaea in 325, where a strict ascetic and celibate position prevailed.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– I don't know

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: One of the most important lent periods in Eastern Christianity is the Great Lent before Easter. It lasts forty days, during which the faithful brethren should abstain from foods, but primarily from personal iniquities. Fasting before Easter, however, was not determined by the early Church as such,

neither in specific days or for certain foodstuff. In the early centuries it was just two days of fast before Easter Sunday. The two days became a whole week later on. The whole week became three weeks in Rome in the 4th century. The three weeks became 5 weeks in Egypt in the 4th century. The 5 weeks became 6 in Antioch and Constantinople in the 4th century, in Jerusalem in the 5th century, in Alexandria in the 7th century. The monks of Palestine would fast for 8 weeks since the 4th century. In Constantinople, an 8th week of moderate fast was added during the 7th century. Some of the early Christians abstained from foods the whole day and ate only in the evenings. Others ate not at all, day or night. The period of fasting was extended to forty days without substantial evidence of any authoritative determination and it should be noted that the Fathers of the first Council of Nicaea (325) were aware of that forty day fasting period.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings

or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: With Emperor Constantine's edict of toleration in 313, the Church found itself with a new role in society, ministering in a public forum and needing a much broader missionary effort to proclaim the Gospel. The needs to modify the liturgical practices also became a necessary response to the appearance of heresies in the 4th century, especially Arianism. The liturgical form developed slowly over time, and it was shaped by the new dynamics of becoming a part of society and combating heresy. During the period under investigation different liturgical forms or rites were developed. Building upon an earlier and for the most part uniform Eucharistic core, efforts were now made to add beauty in the way of ecclesiastical music, iconography, vestments, majestic ceremonial and instruction in theological content.

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On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

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What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

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– Field doesn't know

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized

way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

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– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

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– No

Notes: Celibacy was required only for the monks, not for the laymen and also for the clergy and more particularly for the Bishops. In fact, during the period under investigation, religious and spiritual life blossomed giving rise to monasticism, which became a way for many to strive for the evangelical ideals of asceticism. Monasticism began to influence all aspects of Church life to the point that even the laity began to adopt some of monastic customs and rules. It furthermore became common practice for spouses to separate by mutual consent when they reached old age and both went to live in monasteries. Marriage was still permitted for bishops, but the rule of celibacy for bishops was brought up at the Council of Nicaea in 325, where a strict ascetic and celibate position prevailed.

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– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: It is interesting to note that the distribution of grain in Egypt was often used as a tool for political and diplomatic purposes. For example, Emperor Constantius's attempt in 356 to coerce the civil magistrates into enforcing the expulsion of the Athanasian party from the Alexandrian churches by threatening to withhold the bread of the whole city, of pagans and Christians alike. Just prior to this, in 355, the emperor ordered that the grain should be taken from Athanasius and given to those in communion with the Arian party. Finally, the Arian bishop George (357-361) was accused of having robbed the "houses and loaves of orphans and widows," that is, of having usurped the church's charity system after his occupation of the Alexandrian see.

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: Until the Arab conquest, Egypt was the main resource of the emperors for feeding the population of Constantinople, the army as well as the imperial bureaucracy. It was called the granary of the Empire. The maintenance of regular grain shipments from Alexandria was essential to the stability. According to Athanasius of Alexandria, the leader of the Orthodox party, the grain was in the control of the church for the support of certain widows partly out of Libya, and partly out of Egypt.

Reference: Hollerich, Michael. "The Alexandrian Bishops and the Grain Trade: Ecclesiastical Commerce in Late Roman Egypt". *Journal of the Economic and Social History of the Orient* 25, no. 2 (1982): 187-207. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3632110>.

Reference: Teall, John. "The Grain Supply of the Byzantine Empire, 330-1025.". *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 13 (1959): 87-139. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1291130>.

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The First Council of Nicaea in fact settled the question of the date of the Christian Passover (Easter). This feast is linked to the Jewish Passover, as the crucifixion and resurrection of Jesus occurred during that festival. By the year 300, most Churches had adopted the Western style of celebrating the feast on the Sunday after the Passover, placing the emphasis on the resurrection, which occurred on a Sunday. Others however celebrated the feast on the 14th of the Jewish month Nisan, the date of the crucifixion according to the Bible's Hebrew calendar. The Eastern Churches of Syria, Cilicia, and Mesopotamia determined the date of Christian Easter in relation to the 14th day of Nisan, in the Bible's Hebrew calendar. Alexandria and Rome, however, followed a different calculation, attributed to Pope Soter, so that Christian Easter would never coincide with the Jewish observance and decided in favor of celebrating on the first Sunday after the first full moon following the vernal equinox, independently of the Bible's Hebrew calendar. The Council assumed the task of regulating these differences, in part because some dioceses were determined not to have Christian Easter correspond with the Jewish calendar. The Council of Nicaea, however, did not declare the Alexandrian or Roman calculations as normative. Instead, the council gave the Bishop of Alexandria the privilege of announcing annually the date of Christian Easter to the Roman curia. Although the Council undertook the regulation of the dating of Christian Easter, it contented itself with communicating its decision to the different dioceses, instead of establishing a canon. There was subsequent conflict over this very matter.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Meaning the authorities of the Empire responsible for the order.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Since the times of Diocletian the city of Alexandria had been permitted to keep a portion of the annual shipment of grain to feed its poor. This grant was called variously the "panis", "castrensis", "alimonia" or "trophimon", and it appears to have been maintained until the end of Byzantine rule in Egypt. During the turbulent period between the first Council of Nicaea and the Council of Constantinople, and more precisely in 338, Athanasius of Alexandria, the leader of the Orthodox party, was accused by his adversaries for selling the grain destined to feed the poor of the city for his own profit. Additionally, Emperor Constantine inaugurated an annual subsidy in the cities of the Empire for clerical support and for the care of virgins and widows. This subsidy was temporarily cancelled by Julian but restored by Jovian at a third of the former rate. Similarly, a law of 451 calls for an undiminished continuation of the public assistance to the churches, so that nourishment for the poor may not fail.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: Institutionalized, in a certain degree. In fact, there were several institutions for the care of the elderly, the needy and the infirm both in the capital city, Constantinople, and in other areas of the Empire, which were under the supervision of the Church or of certain Church bishops and/or local organizations. The best known example of such institutions was Basiliads, the charitable/hospital institution founded by Basil of Caesarea in Caesarea of Cappadocia. Earlier there was the orphanage/poorhouse of Zoticus in Constantinople, while there are references to other similar institutions in several major cities of the Empire. It should be mentioned furthermore that the Arians and their supporters maintained similar institutions, in which they offered charitable and medical services. It is known that Aetius, leader of the Anomeans (an extreme group of Arianism) was a physician. In fact, Gregory of Nyssa mentions that such institutions facilitated the propagation of the Arian heresy.

Reference: Miller, Timothy. *The Birth of the Hospital in the Byzantine Empire*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, n.d..

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Exile was one of the major punishments. The other was excommunication and deposition. The Councils that took place during the period under investigation excommunicated several of Arius's adherents, other were deposed while Arius himself was sent to exile. Nestorius was excommunicated by the Council of Ephesus, while the Council of Chalcedon exiled and excommunicated Eutyches and Dioscorus.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Exile was imposed by the Emperor himself. The Councils that took place during the period under investigation ordered, after imperial decision that Arius should be sent to exile, as well as Nestorius at the Council of Ephesus and Eutyches and Dioscorus at the Council of Chalcedon. Furthermore, Emperors attached to Arianism sent to exile Nicene bishops, such as Athanasius of Alexandria, who was exiled five times by four Roman emperors, spending 17 of the 45 years he served as bishop of Alexandria in exile.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted that the state provided to the participating bishops free travel to and from their episcopal sees to the Council at Nicaea, in 325, as well as lodging. These bishops did not travel alone, each one had permission to bring with him two presbyters and three deacons.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: It is interesting to note that the distribution of grain in Egypt was often used as a tool for political and diplomatic purposes. For example, Emperor Constantius's attempt in 356 to coerce the civil magistrates into enforcing the expulsion of the Athanasian party from the Alexandrian churches by threatening to withhold the bread of the whole city, of pagans and Christians alike. Just prior to this, in 355/6, the emperor ordered that the grain should be taken from Athanasius and given to those in communion with the Arian party. Finally, the Arian bishop George (357-361) was accused of having robbed the "houses and loaves of orphans and widows," that is, of having usurped the church's charity system after his occupation of the Alexandrian see.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Since the times of Diocletian the city of Alexandria had been permitted to keep a portion of the annual shipment of grain to feed its poor. This grant was called variously the "panis", "castrensis", "alimonia" or "trophimon", and it appears to have been maintained until the end of Byzantine rule in Egypt. During the turbulent period between the first Council of Nicaea and the Council of Constantinople, and more precisely in 338, Athanasius of Alexandria, the leader of the Orthodox party, was accused by his adversaries for selling the grain destined to feed the poor of the city for his own profit. Additionally, Emperor Constantine inaugurated an annual subsidy in the cities of the Empire for clerical support and for the care of virgins and widows. This subsidy was temporarily cancelled by Julian but restored by Jovian at a third of the former rate. Similarly, a law of 451 calls for an undiminished continuation of the public assistance to the churches, so that nourishment for the poor may not fail.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: Institutionalized, in a certain degree. In fact, there were several institutions for the care of the elderly, the needy and the infirm both in the capital city, Constantinople, and in other areas of the Empire, which were under the supervision of the Church or of certain Church bishops and/or local organizations. The best known example of such institutions was Basiliads, the charitable/hospital

institution founded by Basil of Caesarea in Caesarea of Cappadocia. Earlier there was the orphanage/poorhouse of Zoticus in Constantinople, while there are references to other similar institutions in several major cities of the Empire. It should be mentioned furthermore that the Arians and their supporters maintained similar institutions, in which they offered charitable and medical services. It is known that Aetius, leader of the Anomeans (an extreme group of Arianism) was a physician. In fact, Gregory of Nyssa mentions that such institutions facilitated the propagation of the Arian heresy.

Reference: Miller, Timothy. *The Birth of the Hospital in the Byzantine Empire*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, n.d..

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: Until the Arab conquest, Egypt was the main resource of the emperors for feeding the population of Constantinople, the army as well as the imperial bureaucracy. It was called the granary of

the Empire. The maintenance of regular grain shipments from Alexandria was essential to the stability. According to Athanasius of Alexandria, the leader of the Orthodox party, the grain was in the control of the church for the support of certain widows partly out of Libya, and partly out of Egypt.

Reference: Hollerich, Michael. "The Alexandrian Bishops and the Grain Trade: Ecclesiastical Commerce in Late Roman Egypt". *Journal of the Economic and Social History of the Orient* 25, no. 2 (1982): 187-207. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3632110>.

Reference: Teall, John. "The Grain Supply of the Byzantine Empire, 330-1025." *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 13 (1959): 87-139. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1291130>.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted that the state provided to the participating bishops free travel to and from their episcopal sees to the Council at Nicaea, in 325, as well as lodging. These bishops did not travel alone, each one had permission to bring with him two presbyters and three deacons.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Meaning the authorities of the Empire responsible for the order.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Exile was one of the major punishments. The other was excommunication and deposition. The Councils that took place during the period under investigation excommunicated several of Arius's adherents, other were deposed while Arius himself was sent to exile. Nestorius was excommunicated by the Council of Ephesus, while the Council of Chalcedon exiled and excommunicated Eutyches and Dioscorus.

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Exile was imposed by the Emperor himself. The Councils that took place during the period under investigation ordered, after imperial decision that Arius should be sent to exile, as well as Nestorius at the Council of Ephesus and Eutyches and Dioscorus at the Council of Chalcedon. Furthermore, Emperors attached to Arianism sent to exile Nicene bishops, such as Athanasius of Alexandria, who was exiled five times by four Roman emperors, spending 17 of the 45 years he served as bishop of Alexandria in exile.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The First Council of Nicaea in fact settled the question of the date of the Christian Passover (Easter). This feast is linked to the Jewish Passover, as the crucifixion and resurrection of Jesus occurred during that festival. By the year 300, most Churches had adopted the Western style of celebrating the feast on the Sunday after the Passover, placing the emphasis on the resurrection, which occurred on a Sunday. Others however celebrated the feast on the 14th of the Jewish month Nisan, the date of the crucifixion according to the Bible's Hebrew calendar. The Eastern Churches of Syria, Cilicia, and Mesopotamia determined the date of Christian Easter in relation to the 14th day of Nisan, in the Bible's Hebrew calendar. Alexandria and Rome, however, followed a different calculation, attributed to Pope Soter, so that Christian Easter would never coincide with the Jewish observance and decided in favor of celebrating on the first Sunday after the first full moon following the vernal equinox, independently of the Bible's Hebrew calendar. The Council assumed the task of regulating these differences, in part because some dioceses were determined not to have Christian Easter correspond with the Jewish calendar. The Council of Nicaea, however, did not declare the Alexandrian or Roman calculations as normative. Instead, the council gave the Bishop of Alexandria the privilege of announcing annually the date of Christian Easter to the Roman curia. Although the Council undertook the regulation of the dating of Christian Easter, it contented itself with communicating its decision to the different dioceses, instead of establishing a canon. There was subsequent conflict over this very matter.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

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